

РАЗДЕЛ. ТЕХНИЧЕСКИЕ НАУКИ

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**SOME ASPECTS OF THE ANALYSIS OF MEASUREMENTS, TESTS
AND CONTROL STATE IN ORGANIZATIONS**

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Annotation: The article provides an analysis of regulatory documentation and review of educational literature regulating the analysis of the state of measurements, tests and control at enterprises, identified shortcomings. A list of up-to-date regulatory documentation necessary for the performance of these works has been developed. The relevance of the work on the analysis of metrological support of the educational process and scientific research is shown, which is important for improving the quality of the educational process. Metrological support of the educational process has a significant impact on its quality and competitiveness of university graduates, since conducting training sessions using outdated equipment that is no longer used at enterprises does not form practical skills that will be useful to students in their future professional activities, since they will have to work with completely different measuring instruments. Professional standard 40.012 "Metrology Specialist" provides for the performance of labor

functions "Analysis of the state of metrological support in the department" for the 6th qualification level and "Analysis of the state of metrological support in the organization" for the 7th qualification level, therefore, the formation of such skills is important when training specialists in the field of standardization, metrology and quality management, taking into account the requirements of employers. The methodology have been developed for the formation of skills for analyzing the state of measurements, tests and control in production, in the educational process, scientific research for the development of professional competencies in accordance with professional standard 40.012, the acquisition of competitive advantages of students in the direction of "Standardization and metrology". Examples of the application of the skills of analyzing the state of measurements, tests and control of training are given.

Keywords: professional standard, professional competence, methodology, analysis, measurements, tests, control, metrological support, skills

Introduction.

The GOST (Russian National Standard) R ISO 9000-2015 standard contains requirements according to which an organization must carry out knowledge management, monitoring, measurement and evaluation of processes, products and services [1]. GOST R ISO 9004-2019 also contains provisions concerning the knowledge of the organization: human resources and knowledge of the organization are classified as key resources of the organization according to clause 9.2 and 9.3 of [2], and are recognized as extremely important for achieving the sustainable success of the organization. The introduction of a competence approach and orientation to professional standards in the development of educational programs is aimed at increasing the competitiveness of graduates of higher educational institutions and focusing on the needs of employers in the training of specialists in the field of standardization, metrology and quality management. Professional standard (PS) 40.012 "Metrology Specialist" provides for the performance of labor functions (LF) C/03.6 "Analysis of the state of metrological support in the department" for the 6th qualification level and D/01.7 "Analysis of the state of metrological support in the organization" for the 7th qualification level [3]. Labor actions for LF C/03.6 PS include: "analysis of the staffing of the unit with qualified personnel; analysis of the fund of regulatory documents to ensure the uniformity of measurements; analysis of the condition of measuring instruments, verification scheme; analysis of information on failures of measuring instruments, monitoring, testing during operation, on the state and conditions of their storage, on the efficiency of use" [3]. The analysis of the state of measurements, control and testing is also carried out in preparation for certification of quality management systems, therefore, the formation of such skills

is important to ensure the competitiveness of future metrology specialists, quality specialists (program 27.03.01, 27.04.01, profile “Standardization and quality management”). The professional competence of the masters of the program 27.04.01: “Able to analyze the state of metrological support in the organization” is focused on the PS discussed above.

Article purpose and objectives

The aim of the study is to review and improve normative documentation regulating the issues of analysis of the state of measurements, tests and control in organizations. The main objective of the article is to improve the MS (metrological support) of measurements, tests and control in organizations based on the results of the study of the state of measurements, tests and control in the conditions of enterprises in Sevastopol and Crimea.

Results

The author reviews the normative documentation (ND) for the analysis of the state of measurements, tests and control in organizations. The methodology and procedure for carrying out the work are set out in [4], these recommendations are valid. The recommendations [5, 6] contain general principles for the analysis and evaluation of the metrological support of production in the implementation of ISO 9000 series standards, as well as in the certification of production. However, the list of ND, which should be guided when studying the state of measurements, control and tests in [4] contains expired documents. Thus, it is necessary to improve the regulatory framework governing the analysis of the state of measurements, tests and control in organizations. As a result of the analysis of the list of ND recommended in [4], it was revealed that the following ND from the list are invalid: GOST 8.057-80, GOST 8.207-76, GOST 8.372-80, GOST R 1.11-99, PR RCS (Russian Calibration System) 002-95, RD 50-660-88, RD 50-674-88, MI 81-76, MI 97-76, MI 646-84, MI 1460-86, MI 2005-89, MI 2089-90, MI 2088-90, MI 2125-90, MI 2179-91, MI 2187-92 ICG, MI 2236-92 ICG, MI 2265-93 ICG, MI 2269-93, MI 2277-93 ICG, MI 2278-93 ICG, MI 2281-94 ICG, MI 2284-94 ICG, MI 2334-95 ICG, MI 2365-96 ICG, MI 2386-96 ICG, R RCS 001-95. Updated current versions have been released for 28 of the documents recommended in [4], which must be used when analyzing the state of measurements and control in production. Updated version of ND: GOST R 1.2-2020, GOST R 1.4-2004, GOST R 1.5-2012, GOST 8.315-2019, GOST 8.381-2009, GOST 8.417-2002, GOST 8.532-2002, GOST R 8.563-2009, GOST R 8.568-2017, PR 50.2.007-2001, PR 50.2.014-2002, PR 50.2.014-2002, PR 50.2.015-02, PR 50.2.017-95, PR 50.2.020, MI 1317-2004, MI 1730-87, MI 2146-98, MI 2232-2000, MI 2233-2000, MI 2266-2000, MI 2267-2000, MI 2301-2000, MI 2301-2000, MI 2314-2006, MI 2322-99, MI 2335-2003, MI 2377-98, GOST R ISO 5725-6-2002 (parts 1-6), GOST 8.566-2011, MI 2230-92 ICG, 50.2.038-2004 ICG. The remaining ND recommended in [4] are valid. As a result of the

conducted research, a list of relevant ND (34 documents) has been compiled, recommended for analyzing the state of measurements, tests and control at work, in the educational process, in scientific research.

In the literature offered in electronic library systems, the issue of MS analysis of measurements, tests and control is not sufficiently covered. So, in [7], recommendations according to MI 2240-98 are set out [4], there are no practical tasks on the considered subject in the educational and methodological literature. In [8] this issue is briefly expressed on p. 37. In [9, p.118, 119], the problem of improving the MS is considered, the methodology of analyzing is not described. In order to form the skills of future specialists in metrology, corresponding to LF C/03.6 and D/01.7 PS 40.012 "Metrology specialist" during the study of the course "Metrological support of production", a practical lesson on the topic "Analysis of the state of measurements, control and testing in the organization" is provided, instructional and methodological guidelines for the accomplishment of practical tasks have been developed. Students get acquainted with the methodology and procedure of work according to [4], with forms 1-10 recommended in MI 2240 [4], study ND, and analyze the state of measurements, control and testing of any enterprise at the student's choice. This research is especially useful for masters studying on an individual schedule, since they work in metrology departments, laboratories, quality departments of various organizations, i.e. in accordance with the direction of training and have a large number of practical materials. In the conditions of the university laboratories, students analyze the state of measurements, tests and control in scientific research, in the educational process on the basis of equipment in laboratories and documentation for it. For example, studying the course "Metrological support of production", students of the program 27.04.01 "Standardization and metrology" study the influence of the state of measurements, control and testing on the effectiveness of safety measures in organizations by the example of taking measurements of vibration and sound in the laboratory. Sound and vibration measurements are considered using an analog device "VSHV-003-M", students develop a justification for the need to replace this device with a digital sound meter vibrometer "Ekophysika-110A" for use in the educational process and scientific research.

These studies are also highly relevant, since the equipment used in the educational process is often outdated, requires replacement, is not always provided with verification (calibration) and does not meet the requirements of Federal law No. 102-FZ "On ensuring the uniformity of measurements", the university does not always have a separate metrological service. Metrological support of the educational process has a significant impact on its quality and competitiveness of university graduates, since conducting training sessions using outdated equipment that is no longer used at enterprises does not form practical skills that will be useful to students in their future professional life, since they will have to work with

completely different measuring instruments (MI). The results of laboratory work, scientific research carried out on equipment that is not provided with verification and calibration, may mislead students.

During the analysis of the state of measurements, tests and control, the following are compiled: a list of measuring instruments provided with verification (calibration) and repair, information on the measurement methods and tests, lists of quality parameters of parts, assembly units, products or parameters of technological processes and finished products that are not provided with proper control (measurements), a list of measuring instruments that are not provided with verification (calibration) and repair, information about the company's needs for manufactured measuring instruments, information about quality claims, reliability and other technical characteristics of measuring instruments, control and testing in the organization and others, examples are presented in Tables 1, 2.

Table 1 – List of normative documentation on methods and means of verification and other ND in the field of MS, subject to revision and addition (fragment)

№	Code and ND number	ND name	Comments to ND	Proposals for revision or clarification of individual items
1	EX3.268.0 39 TO	Low-frequency signal generators G3-112	Incomplete description of the device design scheme	Finalize the description of the device design scheme, make all the missing designations
2	2.731.000 TO	Installation for verification of attenuators D1-14 (D1-14/1, D1-14/2)	Non-detailed section “Operating procedure, testing of the device”;	Clarify the section “Operating procedure, testing of the device”
3	DLI2.770. 003 TO	C6-11 Nonlinear Distortion Meter	Information on the range of stable operation of the device (as a percentage of nominal capacity) is not specified	Make edits to the technical description with information on the range of stable operation of the device. For the published editions

№	Code and ND number	ND name	Comments to ND	Proposals for revision or clarification of individual items
				of the technical description, make a note “Attention!” on the first page.
4	I22.044.05 3 TO	Universal oscilloscope S1-65A	Generalized explanation of the knobs and switches located on the front and back panels	Specify the description of the knobs and switches located on the front and back panels of the device.
5	vR3.260.0 18 RE1	The high-frequency signal generator G4-158	Information about the parameters of the external load, which should be used during verification is not specified	Specify the section “Technical characteristics”, and, if necessary, the section “Completeness of the device”
6	2.721.006-02 TO	Digital frequency meter CH3-64/1	The table of the main operations carried out during verification is located between the continuous description of item 11.3 of verification, which makes it difficult to find and perceive information	Move the table “Main operations carried out during verification” before the description of the points of verification
7	EX2.211.0 29 TO	Signal generator of a special form G6-31	Outdated description of the section “Verification”, paragraph 12.1.3 and 12.1.4	Revise the method of verification of specific parameters of the device described in paragraphs 12.1.3 and 12.1.4..

Table 2 – Information about claims to quality, reliability and other technical characteristics of MI, control and testing (fragment)

№	MI name, type, factory designation	Accuracy class	Range measurements	ND for MI	Manufacturer	Year of release	The number of MI	The main claims to the quality of manufacture and technical characteristics	Suggestions for eliminating shortcomings and improving the quality of MI
1	C6-11 Nonlinear Distortion Meter	2	20...199.9 [kHz] 0.3[mV]...100 [V]	GOST 8.331-78 DLI2 770.003 TO	Subsidiary production enterprise "Meridian" Ukraine	1996	2	When manually switching ranges after removing the manual mode, the selected range is not saved	Improvement of the device design
2	Installation for checking volt meters V 1-8	2	U=10 [μV]...300 [V] PG (0.2...0.003/U) % U~10 [μV]...300[V]	YAY 2.761.004 TO	Radio Factory "Punane RET", Tallinn, Estonia	1984	2	Strong influence of noise when working at low voltage	Additional protection of the device from vibrations, externa

			(45, 400, 1000 [Hz])						l noise
3	High - frequency signal generator G3-154	2	Frequency range from 0.1 to 50 [MHz] output voltage adjustment limits from 0 to plus 22 [dBV] (from 1 to 12 [V])	3.26 0.01 5 TO	“Frunze Scientific and Production Association”	19 87	2	Inconvenient use of installation knobs, fixing voltage and frequency	Refine the design of the device, improve the appearance

The analysis of the state of measurements, tests and control in scientific research will be considered by the example of preparation for laboratory accreditation. Documentation, material and technical equipment (MI, testing equipment) of laboratories must meet the requirements of the Accreditation Criteria approved by Order of the Ministry of Economic Development of the Russian Federation No. 707 dated 26.10.2020 (hereinafter referred to as the Accreditation Criteria) and GOST ISO/IEC 17025-2019 in the declared field of accreditation. In accordance with the requirements of paragraph 3 of art.13 of the Federal Law “On ensuring the uniformity of measurements” dated 26.06.2008 N 102-FZ from 24.09.2020, the results of verification of measuring instruments are confirmed by information on the results of verification of measuring instruments included in the Federal information Fund for ensuring the unity of measurements (FGIS Arshin). The analysis of information in research laboratories has shown that the FGIS Arshin does not always have records of the results of MI verification in laboratories. Analysis of the condition of the test equipment showed, for example, that in CAL SB SOI (Chemical and Analytical Laboratory of the Sevastopol Branch of the State Oceanographic Institute) according to ND 52.24.496-2018, it is

necessary to purchase: a thermostatic water bath (water heater thermostat) PE-4034, LB-22-1 or a similar model of any type with a capacity of at least 2 dm³, providing a temperature of (20 ±2) °C, (60±2) °C.

Thus, the results of the analysis of the state of measurements, tests and control are used to improve their metrological support and are also found to be valuable for further research. Typical topics of graduate theses of bachelors of the program 27.03.01 “Standardization and metrology” are “Assessment of the state of measurements at the enterprise”, “Metrological support of the enterprise”, masters of the program 27.04.01 “Standardization and metrology” – “Metrological analysis of technical systems (processes) in order to optimize their metrological support”, “Development of technical measures to ensure the quality of products” and according to the Final State Certification (FSC) programs, students perform these at graduate theses enterprises, for example, FBI “State Regional Center for Standardization, Metrology and Testing in Sevastopol”, FBI “Crimean CSM”, FSUE “SAP”, SUE RC “Krymenergo”, SUE RC “Krymgazset”, etc. The practical result of these theses is the analysis of metrological support (MS) units and the development of measures to improve it. In the process of studying the course “Metrological support of production” by the masters, it is important to form the skills, knowledge and competency necessary to analyze the state of measurements in organizations for further successful implementation of the graduate theses and employment of graduates at enterprises where they undergo pre-graduate practice.

For example, student Troitskaya A.A. examined company's activities, the regulatory and legislative framework in the field of gas supply in the Russian Federation, metrological support for gas flow measurements in the State Unitary Enterprise of the Republic of Crimea “Krymgazset”, the Bakhchisarai Department for the Operation of the Gas Economy and, together with its employees, developed measures to improve it [10]. The following shortcomings of the MI have been identified at the enterprise: outdated devices; there are no devices for metrological maintenance of modern measuring complexes in the laboratory; no internal ND for MI measurements at the enterprise; no quality management system. Troitskaya A.A. studied the technical and metrological characteristics of gas consumption MI: constricting devices, measuring complexes, industrial and residential gas meters, their principles of operation for the development of recommendations for the selection of gas consumption measuring instruments by residential and industrial consumers. To improve the process of gas consumption measurement, it is proposed to use a modern measuring complex “ULTRAMAG”, its metrological and technical characteristics are investigated [10]. In order to verify complexes for measuring the amount of gas “ULTRAMAG”, it was proposed to the enterprise “to purchase means of verification: digital frequency meter CH3-64; digital device for measuring pressure DPI 145; liquid thermostat “Termotest – 100”” [10]. Using these MI, the organization will be able to expand the list of services provided.

Summary

A review of the regulatory documentation regulating the analysis of the state of measurements, tests and control at the enterprise was conducted, shortcomings were identified, a list of relevant ND necessary for the performance of these works was developed. The analysis of the educational literature revealed insufficient coverage of this issue in textbooks on metrology, metrological support of production. It is concluded that the equipment used in the educational process is often outdated, requires replacement, is not always provided with verification (calibration) and meets the requirements of the Federal Law “On ensuring the uniformity of measurements” No. 102-FZ, therefore, the analysis of the state of measurements, tests and control in the educational process and scientific research is relevant. The analysis of the state of measurements, control and tests in the educational process is aimed at the formation of skills provided for by LF C/03.6 and D/01.7 PS 40.012 “Specialist in metrology”. Examples of improvement of metrological support of measurements, tests and control in organizations based on the results of the study of the state of measurements, tests and control in the conditions of standardization and metrology centers, accounting units of measuring instruments of gas supply, heat supply enterprises are given.

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